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**INFLUENCE OF VOLUNTEER MOTIVATIONS TO THE
UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' LEADERSHIP STYLES**

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Psychology

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ABSTRACT

Volunteering is an act of contributing one's efforts and resources freely without any form of tangible compensation. It is a schematic groundwork that scopes diverse aspects into motives, personalities, and social determinants. Numerous studies have been conducted exploring the mediating factors of volunteerism yet, the inclusion of leadership styles in volunteer retention has remained understudied throughout the context. The purpose of this study is to determine the significant influence of volunteer motivation towards leadership styles among 379 college learners in Davao City. This study also accords the 17th Sustainable Development Goal which strives to cultivate multi-stakeholder partnership through capacity development. This study contributes to strengthening both societies and states to implement policies and programs minimizing sociocultural related affairs. Furthermore, the researchers employed quantitative-correlational research design to determine the degree of the relationship between variables in the study. Multivariate regression analysis was also utilized to predict volunteer motivation on leadership styles. The researchers adapted two survey questionnaires: Volunteer Functions Inventory of Clary et al. (1998) and Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire 5x of Avolio and Bass (1995) as research instrument methodologies. Consequently, it has exhibited that there is a significant relationship between volunteer motivation and leadership styles. Positive correlation was found between the volunteer motivation and leadership styles. Hence, only the Protective and Values factor garnered a p-value lesser than the significance level. The current study contributes markedly not only on future research endeavors but also on guiding higher learning institutions in tailoring programs that may strengthen volunteerism and leadership qualities among college learners. Nevertheless, this will enable community organizations and local agencies to reassess their program objectives on the extent of volunteer opportunities available to students. Shaping students' motivation to be proactive in volunteering will intensify their key leadership behaviors.

Keywords: *volunteer motivation, leadership styles, sustainable development goal no. 17, quantitative-correlation, Davao City.*

INTRODUCTION

The crisis precipitated by various health, social, and environmental challenges have petrified aspects of voluntary work throughout society (Tsai et al., 2023). Volunteer literature studies is an intricate schematic groundwork that scopes individual cognition, intertwining various facets (Mason, 2020). Volunteer-related studies play a vital role as they play a catalyst that inculcates a course of action and development. Volunteer motivation refers to individuals' attitudes that employ a functional approach that may serve multiple purposes (Joy, 2020). The functional approach to volunteer motivation integrates various facets, including social, economic, and psychological perspectives, emanating a multidimensional approach. The developing field of volunteer motivation has settled various models that can be inscribed to improve or develop volunteer motivation programs (Wood, 2021). Concurrently, leadership styles have also offered a new scope of volunteer efficiency for humanitarian affiliations under current social schemes. Leadership styles depict the leader's approach and manner within subordinates to perform beyond their capacity (Ekpenyong, 2020). In general, leadership style focuses on how leaders' engagement influences their constituents' behaviors to provide direction and motivation and achieve their objectives, maintaining harmony within the group. (Gutterman, 2023).

Previous studies have revealed that leadership styles shape the degree of commitment among subordinates, which needs to be examined (Chen, 2021). Leadership has amplified the emergence of voluntary work behavior (Isawanto, 2020). For this reason, volunteer motivation has prompted the leadership to procure further literature for future research ventures. Studies underpinning leadership styles and fostering sustained volunteer motivation have remained scarce throughout the scholarly errands (Benevene et al., 2020). Individuals' willingness to volunteer has restrained despite the critical predicament of maintaining the environmental equilibrium. The struggle to maintain active volunteer engagement has still emanated, posing a threat among organizations

(Tsai et al., 2023). To optimize these conflicts, the professional structuring of leading modalities has received more attention in all-volunteer settings (De Clerck et al., 2020).

The demands for search and rescue operations have intensified drastically over the years due to the increase in disasters (Lai & Wang, 2022). Recent events such as floods, bushfires, and pandemics have engrained obstacles throughout humanitarian endeavors and a critical disputation on volunteer reliance throughout communities (O'Halloran & Davies, 2020). Although volunteerism has been recognized in emerging economies, the participation of individuals in voluntary work has declined lately. In a global context, Sweden has recorded 10% of university students dropping out from volunteering activities (Normah & Lukman, 2020). Students' decline in volunteer undertakings has grounded the point that students tend to utilize their time for themselves doing outdoor activities rather than beneficial volunteerism. Normah et al. (2022) presented a report from the Malaysian Youth Development Research Institute revealing that there was also a downturn in youth participation relating to volunteering ventures because low student involvement was also attributed to motivation since the offered volunteer programs did not suffice their needs and the benefits they wanted to obtain.

Meanwhile, in the Philippines, volunteering has been strongly framed regarding community participation development. The Philippine volunteer movement is directly accentuated not only by their pre-colonial values, including *Bayanihan*, which undertakes a community-based support system but also by the active engagement of both public and private counterparts in volunteer development competency (Millora, 2023). Despite the practical volunteer framework, the Philippines' volunteer engagement must also be amplified due to the extreme conditions of climate change. The national volunteer scope must be strengthened since it serves as the first line of defense (Alampay et al., 2019). Respectively, the risks and vulnerabilities linked with climate change may magnify more hazards than before, making communities more vulnerable.

Locally, the Davao region has also attested to disputations embarking on volunteer motivation and student partaking. The student's degree to volunteer has also reached the local context, correlating social competence and civic volunteerism. Most students are no longer involved in community undertakings since they often engage themselves only in neutrality concerning social-related affairs (Roncesvalles, 2022).

As communities undergo modifications throughout centuries, scholarly endeavors on volunteer motivation have prompted new conceptual and theoretical resources to come to terms with the new characteristics of these urban forms. Given the influence of climate change, community landscapes coordinating volunteer work should prepare for mitigation and response work against extreme weather conditions (Alampay et al., 2019). Concurrently, intensifying volunteer motivation could strengthen the means of imposition and revitalization of Global partnership for sustainable development, which is anchored on the 16th and 17th goals under the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals. United Nations (2020) pointed out that the promotion of inclusive and peaceful societies is essential for sustainable development, which in turn results in inclusive, effective, and responsible institutions across different areas, as a partnership for sustainable development equates multi-stakeholders' voluntary commitments including intergovernmental organization, major and minor groups as pathways towards societal betterment. Aside from the environmental alterations, individuals' involvement in volunteer work has also declined, especially in the educational setting, despite initiated volunteering programs (Lim et al., 2020).

Consequently, students' empowerment sculpts a critical disposition under national development since they are considered the future leaders shaping the country (Normah & Lukman, 2020). Accordingly, research on the innovation of volunteer motivation has been disputable because of its underlying motivations, including leadership styles. Studies on leadership behaviors and fulfillment of volunteer motivations by Tsai et al. (2023) affirmed the relationship between

discrete leader behaviors and volunteer motivations. Future research can be designed to map the relationship between leadership styles and pinpoint those leadership styles with precision where they exist. Such findings can facilitate institutions to utilize or hone these behaviors as a trigger to cultivate more volunteers and longer volunteer motivation. The demands correlated with volunteer motivation and leadership cultivate an advancement in the provision of community-based assimilation and the extensive scope of policy-making endeavors, which deepens economic powers and is a pillar for educational initiative measures. In addition, the Philippine National Volunteer Service Coordinating Agency, with the Australian Volunteer Program, conducted the first National Volunteerism Research Agenda, held in May 2022, to address research agendas regarding volunteer-related issues, including the scarcity of research studies tackling volunteerism (Mañosca, 2022). Few research studies have been conducted encroaching on the degree of correlation between volunteer motivation and aspects of leadership, specifically in an educational setting. Also, research studies centering on the strength of the correlation between volunteer motivations and several predictor variables (leadership styles) have not been assessed as much as they should be in the research ventures. Hence, this research aims to fill this gap and emphasize the relationship between volunteer motivation and the different leadership styles.

This study intends to measure the nature and describe the functional relation between college student's volunteer motivations and their respective leadership styles. Thus, the researchers will focus on examining the relationship between these two variables and identifying the leadership style most likely to have greater motivation in terms of volunteerism. Throughout this study, the researchers aim to determine and explore the factors that contribute to the occurrence of this linkage to further the understanding of volunteer motivation to advance this understudied topic. Moreover, the researcher's purpose in conducting this study also lies in tackling the need for volunteers, especially with the ever-growing need for helping hands and the looming threat of disasters that

may strike unexpectedly. Taking that into consideration, the researchers developed three questions that are pertinent to the study. The primary intent of this study is to determine and describe the relationship between volunteer motivations and leadership styles. Specifically, the first is to assess and determine the level of volunteer motivation among students in terms of (a) protective factors, (b) values factors, (c) career factors, (d) social factors, (e) understanding factors, and (f) enhancing factors. Secondly, identify the level of leadership styles in terms of (a) transformational leadership, (b) transactional leadership, and (c) passive-avoidant leadership. Lastly, to determine whether volunteer motivation is significantly influenced by leadership styles among college students.

This research is beneficial to the students because this study's result helps them understand the strength of the relationship between their individual leadership styles and their motivation to volunteer, which could help students utilize this relation to impact the world and on themselves. Moreover, this research will also be beneficial to Higher Education Institutions in Davao City as it paves the way for the advancement of efficient and strengthened volunteerism of the members under them because volunteer training and programs may tailor or incorporate leadership training and seminar to accommodate or work on their styles that yields motivated and efficient volunteers. Lastly, this study benefits future researchers as this topic is relatively understudied, especially in a localized setting. Therefore, future researchers may use this study as a future reference for predicting the relationship between volunteer motivation and leadership styles.

Society has attested to the drastic surge of volunteerism, from its nonprofit organizations across nations to disaster response volunteers that foster security encroaching humanitarian horizons. The paradigm of volunteer literature ventures has undergone dynamic modifications throughout the cities correlating leadership approaches of today's generation. The concurrence of leadership styles with sustainable motivation to volunteer is anchored on the points of Functional Motivation Theory by Clary et al. (1998). This theory posits how

individual motivations could engage one action and serve different psychological functions (Mason, 2020). In this approach, volunteer concern and commitment are channeled through their motives and individual configurations. These motivations include a career that depicts increasing and improving one's professional competence; enhancement which focuses on honing and building one's personal development; social for elevating interpersonal connections; protective in breaking away from distressing feelings; acquiring new abilities and exercising inadequately utilized abilities which entails understanding; and values which demonstrates moral principles based on altruistic beliefs. Nevertheless, this suggests that volunteering has underlying drives depending on the individual scope of cognition.

Full-Range Leadership Theory has also been grounded under the studies to establish the strength of evidence and a focal alternative to bolster the researchers' assumptions throughout the research undertaking. Avolio and Bass (1991) proposed the paradigm of the Full-Range Leadership Model to establish a framework for leadership behavior and ability depending on distinct situations. The full-range leadership theory condenses most leadership perspectives into transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire leadership styles (Serrat, 2020). Concurrently, transformational leadership is subdivided into four dimensions (Lai et al., 2020). Firstly, Idealized attributes are leaders who can exert critical influence and authority over their subordinates; the latter regard them as exceptional individuals, putting their complete trust in them and demonstrating a desire to associate with them and their mission. Secondly, idealized behavior refers to the leaders who can motivate and ingrain dynamics with the group through the vision they think the organization can achieve. Thirdly, inspirational motivation characterizes leaders who inspire and motivate their followers through goals and challenges. Fourthly, intellectual stimulation is the leaders who question their followers' efforts to stimulate innovation and creativity (Howell et al., 2022).

Meanwhile, transactional characteristics include two subdivisions: contingent reward and management by exception (active). The contingent rewards subscale is based on rewards to procure performance improvement—meanwhile, management by exception (active) which defines leaders' penalizing traits. Lastly, the laissez-faire leadership style contains items that bind absent leader behavior (Bennerson, 2021).

METHOD

This section manages the discussion on the means and methodology that the researchers utilize. This incorporates the research design, research instruments, research participants, data gathering procedure, statistical tools, and ethical considerations for this study.

Design and Procedure

The researchers employed a quantitative research design, specifically a descriptive-correlational design, which enabled them to assess the strength of the relationship between college students' volunteer motivations and their leadership styles. According to Cresswell (2022), descriptive correlational design is a form of research where correlational statistics are included; it will be utilized to define and estimate the level of the relationship or association between the chosen variables. Using the quantitative method allowed the researchers to gather more data in a short amount of time and at once. The researchers found this design necessary to verify the presence or absence of a relationship between volunteer motivation and students' leadership styles. This research method does not control or manipulate any of the variables in the study as it merely seeks to investigate relationships between them. This descriptive-correlational study reflected the strength and/or the direction of the relationship between the variables of this study.

Regarding a descriptive correlational research design, the relationship's direction can be positive or negative. It is followed by a questionnaire that will provide the quantitative data needed for analysis. In order to analyze the data

gathered, the researchers used correlational statistics to find out and measure the degree of association between the variables of this study.

This research went through a process that guided the researcher in accomplishing the study. The researchers wrote a letter to conduct the study attributed to the Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences Education (CASE) regarding the authorization of the conduction of the study and the administration of the research instrument to the respondents. After the researchers are permitted, the study is conducted. The consent forms are disseminated, covering the goal and purpose of conducting the study to the participants, along with the study's ethical considerations and the participant's rights. Following the participant's acceptance, the researchers disseminated the survey questionnaires to the respondents. Succeeding the completion of answering, the questionnaires are gathered by the researchers. Following collecting and gathering the questionnaires, the researchers categorized, presented, and interpreted the questionnaire correspondingly.

The statistical tools that the researchers will utilize to be able to analyze and evaluate the gathered data are the following: (1) The mean is a statistical tool that measures the central tendency of a data set by getting the total of all the numbers divided by the number of numbers in that set. (2) Standard Deviation indicates the data set's scattering about its mean (El Omda & Sergent, 2023). In this study, this tool will be used to give an idea about the distribution of scores about the computed mean on the level of volunteer motivation and students' leadership styles at the university. The researchers used this tool to give an idea about the distribution of scores about the computed mean on the level of volunteer motivation and students' leadership styles. (3) Multivariate Regression Analysis is a vital statistical tool that analyzes more than one dependent and independent variable (Dehesh et al., 2019). It will be used to determine the significant influence of volunteer motivation and students' leadership styles. It will also be used to answer the third statement of the problem.

The ethical considerations throughout the research study are as follows: (1) Informed consent form where the researchers gave the potential research participants the liberty to choose whether they would participate. Furthermore, the researchers ensured the participants' answers were fully secured when signing this form. The participants received a printed copy of the guidelines within the conduct of the study. This will be verbally explained beforehand, covering the terms and conditions stipulated in the consent form. The participants were informed of their withdrawal rights and will not be coerced to continue the research. The risks and benefits of the study were stated for the participants' knowledge. (2) Privacy and confidentiality. Researchers obeyed the Data Privacy Act of 2012 in the Philippines. The researchers subjected the answers and identified the respondents to confidentiality. Their identities were kept anonymous, and their responses were only accessed by the researchers, who were held accountable for any branch of information. The researchers ensured the confidentiality of the participant's shared personal information. In addition, the participant's identity was protected at all costs. It entails withholding their name and any other information that could be used to identify them. Additionally, the researchers ensured that the information they provided would not be disclosed to anyone else. (3) Transparency. The researchers were transparent about the aspects of the study that may affect the participants' rights, health, and safety. It also imposes responsibilities for them to disclose information that may affect the integrity of the research.

Respondents

The respondents of this research consist of 379 university students for the school year 2023-2024, Davao City. The researchers selected the participants from these respondents via a random sampling technique. To explain thoroughly, the random sampling technique is the most straightforward probability sampling.

Thus, the respondents of this research were chosen or randomly picked, and the researchers' chosen population does not only fit that description but already resides in the same educational institution as the researchers. The subjects of this

study met the following criteria to become eligible to participate in this study: The respondents must be 18 -25 years old, a bonafide student from one of the Higher Education Institutions in Davao City. The Withdrawal Criteria necessitate that those unwilling to continue participating in this study or those who wish to withdraw can freely and fully withdraw.

Materials and Instruments

In the study, the researchers adopted two research questionnaires: Volunteer Functions Inventory of Clary et al. (1998) and Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire 5x of Avolio and Bass (1995) as research instrument methodologies. Volunteer Functions Inventory of Clary has good psychometric properties to assess volunteer motivation, validated across various volunteer settings and diverse demographics (Alias et al., 2021). Both research instruments underwent pilot testing to ensure the validity and reliability of the two survey questionnaires. The VFI is a self-report questionnaire that consists of 30 separate items. Concurrently, each item is rated on a five-point Likert scale. The proponents of the questionnaire employed a functionalist approach in volunteering where individual motives are subdivided into six functional motives: protective, values, career, social, understanding, and enhancement motives.

Meanwhile, the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire 5x, created by Bass and Avolio, is a leading survey instrument used to assess transformational/transactional leadership (Braathu, 2022). The questionnaire contains 36 self-reported items that pinpoint and quantify key leadership and effectiveness behaviors shown in antecedent studies. Besides, the questionnaire underpins three dimensions of leadership characteristics: transformational, transactional, passive-avoidant, and outcomes of leadership. Concurrently, each dimension coincides with specific scales.

Table 1
Mean Range Matrix of Volunteer Motivation

Range	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
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4.20 - 5.00	Very High	This indicates that volunteer motivation is always demonstrated by the college learners.
3.40-4.19	High	This indicates that volunteer motivation is oftentimes demonstrated by the college learners
2.60-3.39	Moderate	This indicates that volunteer motivation is sometimes demonstrated by the college learners
1.80-2.59	Low	This indicates that volunteer motivation is occasionally demonstrated by the college learners
1.00-1.79	Very Low	This indicates that volunteer motivation is not demonstrated by the college learners

Table 2
Mean Range Matrix of Leadership Styles

Range	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	This indicates that the degree of leadership style preferred by college learners is always demonstrated.
3.40-4.19	High	This indicates that the degree of leadership style preferred by college learners is oftentimes demonstrated.
2.60-3.39	Moderate	This indicates that the degree of leadership style preferred by college learners is sometimes demonstrated.
1.80-2.59	Low	This indicates that the degree of leadership style preferred by college learners is occasionally demonstrated.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	This indicates that the degree of leadership style preferred by college learners is not demonstrated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section highlights the analysis of the findings resulting from this study. The researchers selected a sample of 379 respondents of college students in all year levels from all the college departments at the university. Specifically, this section includes the interpretation of the student's level of volunteer motivation in terms of protective factor, values factor, career factor, social factor, understanding factor, and enhancement factor. This section also interpreted the level of their leadership styles in terms of transformational, transactional, and passive-avoidant. Furthermore, the discussion of this study also revolves around the influence of the students' volunteer motivation and leadership styles.

Table 3
Distribution of Respondents

Year Level	Population	Percentage	Sample Size
1st Year	7980	32%	121
2nd Year	6546	27%	102
3rd Year	5057	21%	80
4th Year	3909	16%	61
5th Year	936	4%	15
Total	24,428	100%	379

Table 3 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in the study, which is detailed according to the accounted year levels. 379 respondents were surveyed in this study, which was analyzed through Raosoft. Based on the analytics, a total number of 121 respondents were allocated for the 1st year students, garnering 32%, 2nd year accumulated 27%, which consists of 102 college students, 3rd year had 80 respondents, which reckoned 21%, 4th year college students have 61 respondents placing 16% on the distribution, and 15 respondents were administered for 5th year college students having 4% adding up to 100%.

Table 4
Level of Volunteer Motivations among College Students

Volunteer Motivation	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Protective Factor	3.40	.813	High
Values Factor	3.84	.708	High
Career Factor	3.80	.730	High
Social Factor	3.62	.789	High
Understanding Factor	3.88	.747	High
Enhancement Factor	3.71	.773	High
Overall	3.71	.664	High

Table 4 presents the level of volunteer motivation among university students and the factors that motivate it in terms of its mean and standard deviation. The overall volunteer yielded an average of 3.71 and is interpreted as having a high degree of motivation to volunteer. This indicates that university students exhibit high volunteer motivation under the factors presented by the Functional Motivation Theory by Clary et al. (1998). Results varied from moderate to high, with the lowest level of volunteer motivation being protective factors, with an average of 3.40, and the highest level of volunteer motivation being understanding factors, with an average of 3.88.

This high degree of volunteer motivation can be explained by different factors acting upon it. The highest factor contributing to volunteer motivation is understanding factors (with an average of 3.88), which are defined as a way to acquire new skills, abilities, and knowledge. This finding is supported by the Liszt-Rohlf et al. (2021) pilot study, where they interviewed 30 volunteers, and 21 of these volunteers stated that they were motivated to volunteer to learn new knowledge and skills. Moreover, a 2023 survey on student success and engagement in higher education concluded that 77% of Filipino students prioritized and wanted to seek skill-based opportunities to find and develop new skills (Chi, 2023). This implication could result in a high degree of understanding

factors as the prevalent motivation to volunteer among university students. Additionally, a high level of volunteer motivation can be attributed to culture, which is associated with social and value motivations placed as the second highest factor in terms of mean under volunteer motivation from Clary et al. (1998) theory, because Filipino university students are in a country that embodies collectivistic culture (Benosa et al., 2021). They are interconnected with a group of people or a society as a whole, which embodies values and norms present within that social group (Cheng et al., 2020).

The protective factor has a mean score of 3.40 with a .813 standard deviation, which means that college learners always demonstrate the motivation to volunteer. Recent research highlights the significance of protective factors in shaping individuals' motivation to volunteer. This aligns with research findings by Gonzalez-Mendez et al. (2020), which indicate that protective factors are less likely to contribute to volunteer compassion fatigue. The research grounded organization support and psychological endurance as significant factors in maintaining volunteer satisfaction and aiding volunteer motivation. A mixture of self-focused motives and other considerations can drive volunteering. Nevertheless, the significance of protective factors in shaping volunteer motivation remains important, indicating an exact interaction between various motivational factors in the decision to volunteer.

This is also supported by the Functional Motivation Theory of Clary et al. (1998), which states that individuals are motivated to engage in activities based on their fulfillment of psychological needs. This theory emphasizes that individuals may have different motives for engaging in volunteering activities, and protective factors may serve as intrinsic motivators, satisfying individuals' psychological needs and leading to sustained engagement in such activities. Moreover, protective factors, such as a sense of belonging, may be perceived as less directly fulfilling psychological needs than other factors. According to this theory, this factor can provide emotional comfort and support, which may not

inherently foster a sense of personal growth and achievement, which are central components of psychological need satisfaction.

In contrast, career, social, and enhancement factors may offer direct avenues for individuals to fulfill their psychological needs. A career factor may provide opportunities for skill development and competence enhancement, while the social factor can satisfy the need for relatedness through interpersonal connections and community involvement. Similarly, the enhancement factor may offer opportunities for personal growth and improvement, aligning closely with fulfilling psychological needs (Tsai et al., 2023). Therefore, while protective factors contribute to overall well-being and motivation, they may be overshadowed by other factors that offer more immediate avenues for psychological need fulfillment.

Table 5

Level of Leadership Styles among College Students

Leadership Styles	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Transformational	3.57	.629	High
Transactional	3.49	.645	High
Passive Avoidant	2.69	.722	Moderate
Overall	3.25	.532	Moderate

In Table 5, the data presents the result of the mean and standard deviation of college learners' level of leadership styles. With 379 participants, college learners' level of leadership style accumulated a mean score of 3.25 and 0.532 standard deviation, constituting a moderate descriptive level for employing leadership styles. Leadership is an associative linkage among students' psychosocial development (Uaikhanova et al., 2022). Asbari et al. (2021) indicated students' leadership abilities include interpersonal skills, work ethics, coordination, problem-solving skills, and flexibility. Developing such leadership abilities enables students to be upskilled for future professional development (Barnes, 2020).

Transformational Leadership Style garnered a mean score of 3.57 and a standard deviation of 0.629. This result shows a high descriptive equivalent, meaning the learners often demonstrate the leadership approach. Anchored in the study by Sokhela and Murhula (2022) with the participants from the University Cork College (UCC), Ireland, showed that the influence of the transformational leadership approach is vital to the student's leadership development since it enables the students to redirect their fellow students' needs through identifying their shared goals, teaching them interdependence, commitment, and collaborative shared decision-making. Concurrently, in the Full-range Leadership Theory of Avolio and Bass (1991), transformational leaders are grounded to motivate and inspire their members to commit to innovation and creativity (Espinosa, 2023).

For the Transactional Leadership Style, college students accumulated a mean score of 3.49 and a standard deviation of 0.645. The results above also indicated a high descriptive scale, which denotes that the learners often demonstrate the leadership approach. The Transactional Leadership Style attained a lower mean score than the Transformational Leadership Style. As anchored in the study of Garger et al. (2023), the Transactional Leadership Style is deemed with criticism since it is inapplicable when students employ creativity, teamwork cohesion, and other facets of effective student-leadership performance. Furthermore, the research revealed that students do not perceive Transactional Leadership as an approach that elevates learning compared to Transformational Leadership Style since elements of Transactional Leadership Style negate learners' satisfaction. Relatively, transactional leadership under the Full-range Leadership Theory underpins fulfilling the members' extrinsic needs, resulting in hindering member empowerment and a conditional process. This has framed Transactional Leadership Theory as disadvantageous for student encouragement (Young et al., 2021).

Passive-avoidant leadership gathered a mean score of 2.69 and a standard deviation of 0.722. The mean score reflected a moderate descriptive index, which

implies that college learners sometimes demonstrate the leadership approach. Comparatively, Passive-avoidant leadership has positioned the lowest mean score from the given leadership approaches. As mentioned in the study of Howard and Knight (2022) on the correlation of leadership style and student academic achievement from the respondents of rural high schools in Alabama, the study discovered that the passive-avoidant leadership style was the least preferred. The researchers asserted that any other leadership style should be reviewed over the given approach when leading schools. These findings could also be underpinned by the theory of Avolio and Bass (1991) since Passiveavoidant leaders remove themselves from supervising and decision-making within the group. The Passive-avoidant leadership type was not coherent at any of the leadership levels (Perpék et al., 2021).

Table 6

Significant Influence of Volunteer Motivation and Leadership Styles.

<i>Predictors</i>	<i>β</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
(constant)	1.417	11.230	.000	
Protective Factor	.115	2.606	.010	Significant
Values Factor	.143	2.527	.012	Significant
Career Factor	.044	.713	.476	Not Significant
Social factor	.037	.816	.415	Not Significant
Understanding Factor	.067	1.071	.285	Not Significant
Enhancement Factor	.089	1.639	.102	Not Significant

$R = .617$
 $= .381$
 $F = 38.165$
 $p = .000$

Table 6 presents the regression between the predictors (Protective et al., Understanding, and Enhancement factors) and Leadership styles as the dependent variable. As the model displayed, the R-Square .381 signifies 38.1% of the variation of volunteer motivation among students, which can be attributed to influence domains of leadership styles. This also indicates that volunteer motivation and leadership style have a direct and weak degree of correlation. Based on the analysis, only Protective and Values Factors are statistically significant since the calculated p-value of Protective factor .010 is lesser than 0.05. Hence, the regression equation is presented as $y = 0.115x_1 + 0.143x_2 + 1.417$ whereby 0.115 is the unstandardized coefficient of the Protective factor, 0.143 is the unstandardized coefficient of the Values factor, and 1.417 is the constant unstandardized coefficient. The equation suggests that as the Protective and Values factor estimates increase, there is an increased prediction for Leadership style association. For instance, given that the value of the protective factor is 3.40, there is an increase of 0.115 in every parameter identified. Meanwhile, 3.84 was the accumulated mean under the values factor, which denotes that an additional 0.143 is expected to increase the level of leadership approach. Based on the model, $y = 0.115 (3.40) + 0.143 (3.84) + 1.417 = 2.357$, 2.357 will be the expected parameters to associate leadership styles linearly.

Protective factors yielded a p-value of 0.01, which is lesser than the alpha level of 0.05; thus, it significantly influences leadership styles. In this context, a protective factor is someone who volunteers to cope with distressing feelings. Stress, or more specifically, manageable stress, can help enhance motivation and performance, as distressing thinking, to a certain degree (i.e., setting lower expectations towards learning), relieves some pressure, which leads to an increase in performance (Gibbons, 2023). This aligns with Nath's (2023) study that concludes stress, or termed eustress, can be an activator towards initiating efforts. Furthermore, it can also push an individual past their limits. This suggests that managing distressing thoughts (i.e., stress) can enhance initiating efforts

such as leadership that enables one to push past their limits. These presumptions are supported by several studies, one of which is Rafique et al. (2022), which states the link between stress and leadership and how the former can be an antecedent for the latter.

The values factor recorded a p-value of .012, which is also less than the predetermined alpha level of 0.05. As pinpointed in the study of Laniya (2021) on a qualitative correlation study of learning servant leadership characteristics and serving as a volunteer leader in business and leadership organizations, volunteer leaders are driven based on their vision, mission, or values, accentuating servant leadership principles. Values factor on volunteer motivation depicts one's core values, including humanistic and altruistic (Martins et al., 2023). Evidence of the study can be grounded theoretically on the Functional Theory of Clary et al. (1998), where volunteers who are motivated based on their values include behaviors helping to grow and leading the members' personal growth. Furthermore, positive correlations between satisfaction and intention to stay were highlighted from leaders' ethical concern and concern for subordinates (Benevene et al., 2020).

Another factor that may explain a significant difference between values and protective factors toward leadership styles is culture. This especially holds in the Philippines, an established collectivist country (Benosa., et al., 2021). Altruistic concepts such as Bayanihan and others are exhibited (Millora, 2023).

According to Erkubilay and Şentürk (2020), altruism has a positive relationship with ethical leadership. Also, altruism is strengthened in a collectivist culture (Booyesen et al., 2021). This suggests that altruistic values significantly influence Filipinos' leadership styles. Culture may also be a factor in why distressing feelings can significantly influence leadership style. In Filipino culture, the "tagasalo personality" has characteristics of someone who is urged to take responsibility, be a mediator, prioritize others over self, and take care of others (Tuazon et al., 2021).

Furthermore, an individual who exhibits a "tagasalo personality" may struggle with internal anxiety and stress. Thus, they act out, which alleviates the said distressing feelings (Go Tian-Ng, 2023). This suggests that the culturally unique concept of a "tagasalo" in Filipino culture, or in this context, someone with distressing thoughts and feelings might influence leadership as a way of alleviation, especially as someone with the tendency to take responsibility and see others as a priority and someone to be taken care of, which is a core characteristic of a leader.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section presents the study's conclusion and recommendations based on the findings and outcomes.

Conclusion

As universities have undergone modifications to integrate socially with both local and global communities, students' social character has progressed profoundly. The decline of volunteer motivation has prevailed recently, but only some studies are under academic literature. Studies pertaining to students' motivation to volunteer revealed that low voluntary engagement has been recorded, prompting a critical disposition under social affairs. This occurrence influences not only personality growth but also in shaping social values as responsible citizens. Concurrently, leadership styles have also been associated with volunteer motivation. However, studies on volunteer motivation and leadership styles have yet to be studied.

College students across all the departments in the study have a high level of volunteer motivation and a moderate level of leadership styles. The university's active participation in community engagement has cultivated students to acknowledge not only their academic potential but also to be socially aware of their responsibilities as citizens. Apprehending their open obligation relative to advancing modern social values has framed a societal groundwork for every learner in higher learning institutions. Furthermore, the functional motives

under volunteer motivation presented in the study have indicated that college learners are diverse and innately driven to be active on community uptrends. As presented, college learners have an established sense of social responsibility since they are able to reckon with their own purpose in volunteering.

College students garnering a moderate degree of leadership styles constitute a general attribute of the university's profile in mounting a conducive environment for learners' engagement. This may be anchored on learners' preferences for leadership roles or subordinate tasks. Although college learners can be proactive in social contexts, being a leader equates to complex tasks. Leadership is multifaceted coverage of one's skills, personalities, and behaviors, leading to active leader-follower engagement. Strengthening leadership roles among college students requires re-imagining the school's mission, vision, and goals. Formalizing programs, partnerships, training, seminars, and projects could improve the school's leadership inclinations. Aside from the internal framework, entailing continual teaching and tailored leadership literacy among the school's facilitators, professors, and other sectors could contribute to strategic leadership among the students.

This study has substantiated a positive coefficient correlation regarding volunteer motivation and leadership styles, which indicates a direct relationship between variables. As motivation to volunteer increases, parameters to demonstrate a distinct leadership style also increase. Consequently, the null hypothesis is also rejected since volunteer motivation significantly influences leadership styles. Such information conveys that volunteer motivation is significant in determining leadership roles. College students become more active when their volunteer motives are integrated with their key leadership behaviors. Among the six factors in functional volunteer motivations, only Protective and Values factors have significantly influenced leadership styles. The protective factor suggests that individuals volunteering tend to disengage themselves from negative feelings. Volunteers who are directed and trained are more likely not to be distracted by their personal issues, enhancing their protective mechanism.

Nevertheless, an environment for supportive leadership affects volunteer retention. Meanwhile, the Values factor illustrates one's altruistic and humanistic principles toward others. Leaders who are motivated by the Values factor can inspire the organization's goals, which increases their motivation to volunteer and attracts more individuals to volunteer.

Recommendations

University students can capitalize on the insights gleaned from this study by actively engaging in volunteer activities and seizing opportunities to develop their leadership skills. Recognize the value of volunteerism in contributing to the community and personal growth and skill enhancement. Take the initiative to explore various volunteer opportunities available within the university and the wider community, aligning with my interests and values.

Higher education institutions in Davao City are pivotal in fostering a culture of volunteerism and leadership development among students. Integrate service-learning components into curricula across disciplines, allowing students to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world contexts while cultivating leadership skills. Collaborate with community organizations and local agencies to expand the scope of student volunteer opportunities and establish support systems to empower students to participate in volunteer activities and actively enhance their leadership potential.

Future researchers interested in exploring the influence of volunteer motivation towards leadership styles among college students can build upon the foundation laid by this study. Utilize mixed-method approaches, incorporating qualitative and quantitative, to understand better the underlying mechanism and factors influencing the relationship between volunteerism and leadership. Moreover, by adopting a comprehensive and interdisciplinary approach, future research endeavors can contribute valuable insights to the fields of volunteerism and leadership development.

Concerning the university's psychology program, this study accords with shaping psychology students' motivation to volunteer and partake in leadership behaviors. This study amplifies comprehension of the student's motives and behavioral disposition in undertaking voluntary work. Assessing these aspects could integrate conducive learning and volunteer retention among psychology program students. Aside from that, this study will serve as a groundwork for the program's coordinators, professors, and staff to implement functional learning programs and lessons assimilating effective leadership and cultivating volunteer motivation. Moreover, from exploring commonalities to generating in-depth analysis, instigating college learners' volunteer engagement and leadership roles have encrypted a cornerstone for the program to reinforce their students' potential throughout time.

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